

STIMULANTS OF AGRICULTURE CROPS BASES QUINAZOLIN-4-ONE

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Annotation: The article for the first time presents the method of synthesis of coordination compounds of quinazolin-4-ones. Studied the quinazolin-4-one with 3-oil acids studied the methods of synthesis of coordination with synthesis of coordination.

Key words: quinazolin-4-one, 3-oil acid, synthesis of coordination, synthesis of coordination, ethanol, antranil acid, formamid.

INTRODUCTION

Complex compounds occupy an important place in the life of the flora and fauna. For a long time, scientists were interested in studying the biochemical processes that go to the plant, animal and human organism. As a result of long studies, by the end of the 19th century, all chemical compounds were divided into two categories: one of these is atomic compounds and the other molecular (or complex) compound, which received the name of compounds. Later, the first different compounds are called compounds of the first order, and the second-compounds of the higher order. $CuCl_2$, BF_3 , NH_3 , $FeCl_2$ substances such as are among the compounds of the first order, whose formation is subject to the valence rule. Compounds of the upper order are formed as a result of the interaction of one simple compound with another simple compound, later relatively stable ones of high-order compounds were called complex (coordination) compounds. A coordination compound is a compound whose molecule or ion has a center ion or atom, which is surrounded by several ions or molecules, that is, ligands. The complex compound seeks to maintain its independence even in solutions, dissociating into ions. When the positive charge of the central ion is more than the sum of the negative charges of the ligands surrounding it, such a complex is a cation complex, when the charge of the central ion is smaller than the sum of the charges of the ligands surrounding it,

the anion complex is called a neutral complex, when the charge of the central For example, chlorophyll, a substance that is found in the green part of plants and that carries out photosynthesis, is a coordination compound of magnesium, a substance that supplies living cells to the with oxygen – a coordination compound of blood hemoglobin iron. The coordination compound I combinations, exchanges, redox reactions are us. Currently, the Earth's content is increasing in alkalinity, or acidity, due to the treatment of most lands with mineral substances[1,2].

Obtaining herbicides, dyes, substances that enhance plant growth, stabilizers is an important task of today. The actual problem of today is the growth and development of plants, consisting in the synthesis of minerals that will be needed to increase their yield. These synthesized substances are more efficient than other synthesized substances, the synthesis methods are also faster, low-cost is more economically profitable and has a slightly faster increase in plant development, growth, yield.

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These compounds, by their nature, form complex compounds, both five-membered and six-membered. Quinazoline-4-on and its gamologists are of theoretical and practical importance among all heterocyclic compounds, making these compounds have a high physiologically active property within heterocyclic compounds, so these compounds are used in obtaining herbicides, dyes, plant growth enhancers, stabilizers [3,4,5].

EXPERIMENTAL PART.

1. Synthesis of quinazoline-4-on.

0.1 moles of anthranilic acid and 0.4 moles of formamide are placed in a tube with a rounded bottom.

The reaction mixture was heated for 1 hour at 150°C through a reverse cooler in the Woodda alloy, then cooled to room temperature. When placed in cold water, white crystals were formed, filtered, dried, recrystallized in alcohol.

The reaction takes place as follows.

2. Effect of quinazolin-4-on with 3-indolic fatty acid.

0.2 moles of quinazolin-4-on and 0.2 moles of 3-indolic fatty acid are placed in a tube with a rounded bottom.

The reaction mixture was heated for 3 hours at 80°C in a water bath in an inverted refrigerator, then cooled to room temperature. When placed in cold water, yellowish crystals were formed, filtered, dried, recrystallized in alcohol.

N³-indolyl quinazolin-4-on-the formation of a coordination compound with cobalt II-nitrate of 4-on. The product of the effect of 0,2 mole of Quinazolin-4-on with 3-indolic fatty acid 0,1 mole of cobalt II-nitrate is placed in a porcelain mortar and mixed with a blender for 3 hours. Every 10-15 minutes while stirring, the porcelain is cleaned by scraping the area around the mortar and the blender. The formula of the compound can be expressed as follows. It was learned that this compound has the peculiarity of growing plants.

Literature:

1.Fozil E.Saitkulov, Azamat A.Tashniyazov, Azimjon A.Mamadrahimov, Kh.M Shakhidoyatov. 2,3-Di-methyl-quinazolin-4(3H)-one. 2014/7/1. magazine Acta Crystallographica Section E: Structure Reports Online. №7 pp.o788-o788.

2. Сaitkulov Ф. Э., Гиясов К., Элмуратов Б. Ж. Метилирование 2-метилхиназолин-4-она «мягкими» и «жесткими» метилирующими агентами // Universum: химия и биология. – 2022. – №. 11-2 (101). – С. 49-51.
3. Сaitkulov Ф.Э., Элмуратов Б.Ж., Гиясов К. АЛКИЛИРОВАНИЯ ХИНАЗОЛИН-4-ОНА "МЯГКИМ" И "ЖЕСТКИМ" АЛКИЛИРУЮЩИМИ АГЕНТАМИ // Universum: химия и биология : электрон. научн. журн. 2022. 1(103) стр. 53-57.
4. Saitkulov, F. E. Ropijonova, N.SH, Elmuradov, B. J. (2022). Methylation of Quinazolin-4-One with "Soft" and "Hard" Methylating Agents. International Journal of Development and Public Policy, 1(8), 97–101.
5. G.O. Boymuratova, F.E. Saitkulov, Kh.M. Nasimov, J. G'.Rahimov, & M.Tugalov. (2022). To Examine the Processes of Biochemical Action Of 6-Benzylaminopurine with Cobalt-II Nitrate Dihydrate on the "Morus Alba" Variety of Moraceae Plant. Eurasian Journal of Physics, Chemistry and Mathematics, 3, 39–42.
6. Сaitkulov Ф. Э., Элмуратов Б. Ж. УФ-спектральные характеристики хиназолин-4-он и -тионов. Innovative developments and research in education international scientific-online conference. pp-10-12
7. Saitkulov f. et al. biochemical nutrition family plant rute-lemon leaved // Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 17. – С. 268-273.
8. Murodillayevich, Kholmiraev Mekhroj, Khaydarov Gayrat Shoyimovich, and Saitkulov Foziljon Ergashevich. "Chromoto-Mass Methods for Detecting Simple Esters in Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry Method." INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BIOLOGICAL ENGINEERING AND AGRICULTURE 1.6 (2022): 53-56.
9. Saitkulov, Foziljon, et al. "CARBOHYDRATES ARE THE MAIN SOURCE OF ENERGY IN THE BODY." Solution of social problems in management and economy 1.7 (2022): 68-71.
10. Ergashevich, Saitkulov Foziljon, et al. "Photochemical Processes Photosynthesis Pathway On House Plants Leaves" Black Prince". Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences 10 (2022): 76-78.
11. Saitkulov, Foziljon, et al. "THE ROLE IN THE PLANT AND THE FUNCTIONS OF NUTRIENTS." Инновационные исследования в науке 1.16 (2022): 29-31.
12. Saitkulov, F., Eshqobilov, J., Turgunova, N., & Xamidov, A. (2022). PLANT NUTRITION, THE PROCESS OF ABSORPTION. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 1(7), 25-29.

13. Saitkulov, Foziljon, et al. "TITRIMETRIC ANALYSIS OF CALCIUM CATION IN" OBI NAVVOT" VARIETY OF MELON." Академические исследования в современной науке 1.19 (2022): 302-304.
14. Saitkulov, Foziljon, et al. "BIOCHEMICAL EFFECTS OF THE COORDINATION COMPOUND OF COBALT-II NITRATE QUINAZOLIN-4-ONE WITH 3-INDOLYL ACETIC ACID IN THE "AMBER" PLANTS GRADES PHASEOLUS AUREUS." Академические исследования в современной науке 1.17 (2022): 263-267.
15. Saitkulov, F., Khudayarov, M., Hikmatova, D., Sharipova, K., & Khamidov, A. (2022). QUANTITATIVE METHOD FOR THE DETERMINATION OF NITRATE USING DIPHENYLAMINE. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 1(6), 187-190.
16. Saitkulov, Foziljon, et al. "STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF FERTILIZING ON GRAIN PRODUCTIVITY." Development and innovations in science 1.17 (2022): 32-35.
17. Saitkulov F. et al. PLANT NUTRITION, THE PROCESS OF ABSORPTION //Current approaches and new research in modern sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 7. – С. 25-29.
18. Saitkulov F. et al. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE USE OF FATS //Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 7. – С. 175-177.
19. Saitkulov F. et al. THE ROLE IN THE PLANT AND THE FUNCTIONS OF NUTRIENTS //Инновационные исследования в науке. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 16. – С. 29-31.
20. Saitkulov, F., Qilichyeva, N., Abdullayev, B., Anvarov, A., & Ergasheva, M. (2022). TITRIMETRIC ANALYSIS OF CALCIUM CATION IN" MEGATON" VARIETY OF CABBAGE. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 2(10), 134-135.